

16 NRM02 SURFACE
Deliverable 5

Version 0.7

**Pre-normative guidelines for measurement methods and procedures, including
spectral properties, effects of measurement uncertainty in tolerance
calculations obtrusive light and light pollution of road lighting
installations**

EMPIR GRANT Agreement 16NRM02 SURFACE

Draft 0.7

Mikael Lindgren – RISE, Research Institutes of Sweden AB, Borås, Sweden
Valérie Muzet – Cerema, Research team ENDSUM, Strasbourg, France
Paola Iacomussi – INRIM, Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica, Torino, Italy
Johana Bernasconi – METAS, Federal Institute of Metrology, Berne-Wabern, Switzerland
Dominique Renoux – LNE, Laboratoire National d'Essais, Paris, France
Sébastien Liandrat – Cerema, Research team ENDSUM, Strasbourg, France
Toomas Kubarsepp – Metroserf, Tallinn, Estonia
Farshid Manoocheri – AALTO, Espoo, Finland

D5 deliverable of the EMPIR Joint Research Project

16NRM02 SURFACE

Title	:	Pre-normative guidelines for measurement methods and procedures, including spectral properties, effects of measurement uncertainty in tolerance calculations obtrusive light and light pollution of road lighting installations
Reference	:	EMPIR 16NRM02
Due Date of the deliverable	:	29 February 2020
Actual submission date of the Deliverable	:	29 December 2020
Dissemination level	:	PUBLIC EMBARGO UP TO June 2022
Author(s)	:	Mikael Lindgren Valérie Muzet Paola Iacomussi Johana Bernasconi Dominique Renoux Sébastien Liandrat Toomas Kubarsepp Farshid Manoocheri
Keywords	:	Luminance coefficient, Geometries, Measurement condition,
Abstract	:	<p>The design of a road lighting system should be based on the knowledge of the <i>actual</i> luminance coefficient (in the direction of emission of road lighting luminaires and the direction of observation) for the actual road. Because the actual quantity of q is not known, nor is listed as reference values in the EN standard (it provides only the directions in which q should be known), designers use in the calculations as q reference values the ones given in CIE 144 scientific publication. These values have been established from measurements on several road surfaces made in the mid-1970s and are obviously not representative of current road surfaces nor have uncertainty values. The low reliability of the available q data is well known: to be sure to reach the luminance standard requirements and avoid controversy with the customers, designers introduce an heuristic over-dimensioning of the installed luminous flux which compensates for the supposed depreciation due to ageing.</p> <p>This deliverable first presents quantities and practices of road lighting with a focus on road photometry. available data and measuring devices among SURFACE project are done in accordance with the bibliography. In the second part, review and suggestions on measurement procedures for on-site and laboratory measurements are presented. The last part of the guideline is on additional aspect including impact of spectral behaviour.</p>
Contact	:	https://surface-nrm02.eu

About the EMPIR

The European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) coordinates research projects to address grand challenges, while supporting and developing the SI system of measurement units. There is an increased focus within EMPIR on innovation activities to target the needs of industry and accelerate the uptake of research outputs. The programme's capacity-building projects aim to bridge the gap between EU member states with emerging measurement systems and those with more developed capabilities. The EMPIR is jointly supported by the European Commission and the participating countries within the European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET e.V.). The EMPIR will ensure collaboration between National Measurement Institutes, reducing duplication and increasing impact. The overall goal of the EMPIR is to accelerate innovation and competitiveness in Europe whilst continuing to provide essential support to underpin the quality of our lives.

See <https://msu.euramet.org> for more information

About 16NRM02 SURFACE

SURFACE aims at providing metrological foundations for the photometric characterisation of road surfaces in order to realise lighting systems, such as smart and adaptive lighting systems. The project is a Joint Research Project coordinated by INRiM, belonging to the European Metrology Research Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) of the European Metrology Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET). See <https://surface-nrm02.eu> for more information.

SUMMARY

The design of a road lighting system should be based on the knowledge of the *actual* luminance coefficient (in the direction of emission of road lighting luminaires and the direction of observation) for the actual road. Because the actual quantity q is not known, nor is it listed as reference values in the EN standard (it provides only the directions in which q should be known), designers use in the calculations as q reference values the ones given in the CIE 144 scientific publication. These values have been established from measurements on several road surfaces made in the mid-1970s and are obviously not representative of current road surfaces nor do they have uncertainty values. The low reliability of the available q data is well known: to be sure to reach the luminance standard requirements and avoid controversy with the customers, designers normally introduce an heuristic over-dimensioning of the installed luminous flux which compensates for the supposed depreciation due to ageing.

This deliverable first presents quantities and practices of road lighting with a focus on road photometry. Available data and measuring devices within the SURFACE project are presented in accordance with the bibliography. In the second part, a review and suggestions on measurement procedures for on-site and laboratory measurements are presented. The last part of the guideline deals with additional aspects including the impact of spectral behaviour.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	3
2	QUANTITIES AND GEOMETRIES	5
2.1	Road surface measurement parameters.....	5
2.2	Measurement geometries according to CIE and Standards requirements	7
2.2.1	<i>Impact on lighting pollution</i>	<i>10</i>
2.3	SURFACE project analysis of geometries	11
3	GUIDELINES ON METROLOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR PORTABLE AND LABORATORY INSTRUMENTS	14
3.1	Metrological requirements of laboratory instruments	14
3.2	Measurement parameters and geometries	14
3.2.1	<i>Measurement conditions and parameters contributing to the uncertainty.....</i>	<i>16</i>
3.2.2	<i>Summary of the metrological requirements to measure r-tables</i>	<i>18</i>
4	GUIDELINES FOR LABORATORY MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES	19
4.1	Sample preparation and marking	19
4.1.1	<i>General information.....</i>	<i>19</i>
4.1.2	<i>Road extraction</i>	<i>19</i>
4.1.3	<i>Laboratory confection</i>	<i>20</i>
4.1.4	<i>Transport and storage</i>	<i>20</i>
4.2	Setup alignment	20
4.3	Measurement methods.....	21
4.3.1	<i>Absolute method</i>	<i>21</i>
4.3.2	<i>Relative method</i>	<i>21</i>
4.4	Measurement conditions	21
5	GUIDELINES FOR ON-SITE MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES.....	23
5.1	Road site definition – measurement conditions	23
5.2	Road condition – selection of the measurement area	23
5.3	Measurement conditions	23
5.3.1	<i>Measurement area selection.....</i>	<i>24</i>
5.3.2	<i>Common practices concerning the number of measurements</i>	<i>25</i>
5.3.3	<i>Description of the measurements</i>	<i>26</i>
5.4	Data analysis	27
5.4.1	<i>Specific approach for on-site measurements data analysis.....</i>	<i>27</i>
6	GUIDELINES FOR CONSIDERING ADDITIONAL ASPECTS.....	29

6.1	State of the pavement considering dirt, and impact of traffic	29
6.2	Tolerances and uncertainties	32
6.3	Spectral properties of the pavement	34
6.4	Impact of the lamp spectral power distribution	36
6.4.1	<i>Methodology</i>	36
6.4.2	<i>Impact of source SPD on the measured values</i>	37
6.4.3	<i>Impact of source SPD on the calculated uncertainty values</i>	42
7	CONCLUSIONS	44
8	REFERENCES	48

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. The photometric characteristics of the road surface depend on the angles of observation α , deviation β and incidence ε . By convention, according to CIE 066 and CIE 144 guidelines and road lighting standards, for the characterisation of road photometry, α is set at 1°	6
Figure 2. Luminance coefficient indicatrix, presented by De Boer in 1967.....	6
Figure 3. Projection in 2D of the reflection indicatrix.....	6
Figure 4. Schematic representations of the conventional geometry for the photometric characterisation of road markings according to EN 1436, which defines a nominal observation angle of 2.29° corresponding to an observation distance of 30 m and a driver’s eye height of 1.2 m. a. Geometry for the measurement of the retroreflection factor R_L : the illumination angle is set to 1.24° . b. Geometry of the measurement of the luminance coefficient under diffuse illumination Q_d . The integrating sphere creates a diffuse illumination from the light source placed in the middle of the sphere.....	8
Figure 5. a) Example of a luminance image taken with a luminance camera. The areas corresponding to different angles of observation are shown. b) Corresponding luminance measured with the concept of a moving observer.....	10
Figure 6. Theoretical model for light pollution evaluation of the light emission of town.....	11
Figure 7. A schematic of a measurement setup. The field of view is limiting the measured area.....	14
Figure 8. A schematic of a measurement setup. The illumination determines the measured area.....	15
Figure 9. A schematic of the non-uniformity of the illumination, both angularly and spatially.....	15
Figure 10. A schematic of the effect due to the angular subtense of the source. A point of the illuminated surface receives light from different parts of the source.....	16
Figure 11. A schematic of the angular subtense of the detector. The detector sees a point of the surface within a range of angles.....	16
Figure 12. An example of the marking of the measured surface of a sample.....	19
Figure 13. An example of the marking of the observation direction of a sample. The tape should not be left on the measured surface as it may alter the surface of the sample. The indication of the observation direction and the name of the sample should be put on the backside or on the sides.....	20
Figure 14. Typical multilane divided roadway. Sampling sites or measurement sites should be identified with reference to lane, tyre track or centre, driving direction, etc.....	23
Figure 15. General view of a road pavement where tyre tracks within lanes are visible.....	24
Figure 16. Contour gauge for the identification of road surface irregularities: a) dimensions, b) simulation on site.....	24
Figure 17. a) An example of position marking in a Swiss tunnel. The exact measurement location can be retrieved from the plan of the tunnel and the number (here N5:430:050). b) Example of measurement of lateral position relative to a marking.....	25
Figure 18 : Example of precise localisation of measurements points. In the picture, the words “lane” or “line” is used instead of “track”.....	25
Figure 19. Close-up views of different pavements before measurement with a portable device. An object or a ruler is used to provide a scale and an idea of the colour of the pavement.....	27
Figure 20. Illustration of the heterogeneity of the photometry of cement concrete pavements. The photometric measurements were done with Coluroute portable device on the new pavements (T0 in red), after 6 months	

(in yellow), 18 months (in green) and 30 months (in blue). The centre track measurements are represented by triangles and the tyre track measurements by circles⁵⁵. In the graph legend, the word “lane” is used instead of “track”. 29

Figure 21. Illustration of the age and traffic effect on a circulated typical French pavement whose photometry was measured every 6 months during 3 years with Coluroute portable device⁵¹. The centre track measurements are represented by triangles and the tyre track measurements by circles. In the graph legend, the word “lane” is used instead of “track”. 30

Figure 22. Positions of the ten measurements for each site. From Ref. 49. 31

Figure 23. Q_0 and S_1 for asphalt concrete (AC for asphalt concrete and OGPA for open graded porous asphalt) surfaces in a) and for chipseal surfaces (surface dressing) in b). The arrow shows the direction of movement from shoulder to tyre track (solid circle = shoulder value, arrowhead = tyre track value). From Ref. 49. 31

Figure 24 The relative tolerance in the luminance value versus the uncertainty in the knowledge of the road luminance coefficient and luminaire luminous flux 33

Figure 25. Spectral effects of the asphalt surface characteristics of aging from the ASD ground spectral measurements (the major water-vapor absorption bands are interpolated). A, asphalt aging and erosion; B, structural road damages (cracks); C, structural road damages (raveling); D, pavement maintenance. From Ref. ⁶³ 35

Figure 26. Spectral reflectance of the test set of nine road pavements used in the calculations. 37

Figure 27. a) Deviations of the Relative Luminance Coefficient and b) standard deviations, of test set road surfaces for the different light sources. 38

Figure 28. a) Deviations of the Relative Luminance Coefficient of each road surface and b) standard deviations, of test set road surfaces for different LED sources. 39

Figure 29. Cumulated values of the different light sources on the test set road surfaces. 41

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Stopping distance at different driving speeds (according to the authors’ country driving code). 12

Table 2. Distances which correspond to different nominal observation angles at 1.5-m height of observer. 12

Table 3. SURFACE recommendation for new geometries. 12

Table 4. Measurement quantities and calibration factors. 17

Table 5. Measurement uncertainty contributions. 17

Table 6. Requirements for optimal laboratory measurement conditions. 18

Table 7. Test road surface luminance coefficient boundaries for large set of 184 SPD, case A calculations. 42

Table 8. Luminance coefficient mean value, standard deviation and interval calculated with MCM of the variation of three given light sources SPD. 43

Table 9. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations. 44

1 INTRODUCTION

Specifications concerning road lighting and the photometry of road surface were established more than 40 years ago. However, pavement surface characteristics are crucial for functional quality and safety of roads, related not only to its mechanical and dynamic performance, but also to its visual performance and the safety at night of all road users. In Europe there are 5 Million kilometres of roads¹, about the 40 % of them are lit, according to three different European countries Road National Administrations, by lighting systems designed considering photometric performance of pavements published in a technical documents of the 1970s². Currently, road lighting installations must comply with the directives of the European Road Lighting Standards³.

Considering the physical property of the pavement, the luminance coefficient q of the road links the illuminance (linearly proportional to energy consumption) with the luminance related to the visual performance, described by a vision model which defines the luminance values required to recognize obstacles on the road. The latter is not linearly linked to the energy consumption.

Designers determine the required number and spacing of road luminaires along a road to fulfil the requirements for road luminance and quality parameters values, given in the EN Standard⁴ with the additional goal of energy optimization.. To do these calculations based on luminance criterion, designers use reference data of r values (called *r-tables*) published in the CIE 144 document⁵. However, these *r-tables* are derived from measurements carried out more than 40 years ago. The photometric properties of the road materials have evolved over time^{6,7} and reference data is not available. Furthermore, the reliability of the data is unknown because no statement about measurement uncertainty is presented.

The energy consumption in Europe used for lighting amounts to 14 % of the total energy consumption (data from 2011)⁸. This is the reason for the large impact on energy savings achievable with suitable actions on lighting. For road lighting, actions should start already at the design stage, by the use of more reliable and optimized q data as well as design methods specific for smart lighting.

The introduction of energy performance indicators into the European standard⁹ and its correlated requirements pushed forward the optimization of the lighting system, not only in the design of luminaires and in the selection of their luminous intensity distribution, but also in the installation layout and in obtaining and maintaining the lighting level at the minimum value required by the standard. This last aspect can be solved by the use of adaptive lighting systems equipped with a luminance measurement system: a continuous monitoring of the road luminance can reduce the energy consumption to a minimum. The energy optimization requires reaching the luminance prescribed by road lighting standards with the lowest energy consumption. The advantages are not only in energy usage, but at lower illuminance the luminous flux reflected by the illuminated surfaces (road, buildings and grass, etc.) will be lower too, therefore the sky luminance (i.e., the lighting pollution) will be reduced.

The design of a road lighting system should be based on the knowledge of the *actual* luminance coefficient (in the direction of emission of road lighting luminaires and the direction of observation) for the actual road. Because the actual quantity of q is not known, nor is listed as reference values in the EN standard (it provides only the directions in which q should be known), designers use in the calculations as q reference values the ones given in CIE 144 scientific publication⁵. These values have been established from measurements on several road surfaces made in the mid-1970s and are obviously not representative of current road surfaces nor have uncertainty values. The low reliability of the available q data is well known: to be sure to reach the luminance standard requirements and avoid controversy with the customers, designers introduce an heuristic over-dimensioning of the installed luminous flux which compensates for the supposed depreciation due to ageing. These values are not adequate for designing against requirements of vision performance, optimisation, and energy consumption of modern lighting installations for several reasons:

- The properties of current pavements have progressively changed, and some studies show that using the current standards, based on available CIE data, may lead to errors on average luminance often over 30 % and sometimes over 50 %¹⁰. Moreover, the photometric properties of the road materials can change significantly over time¹¹⁻¹³.
- New types of luminaires, especially those using Solid State Lighting (SSL), have very sharp luminous intensity distributions; this simplifies the energy consumption optimisation but increases the influence of the road surface reflective characteristics, especially when luminance and/or uniformities are considered.
- SSL including current LED technology supports smart lighting, and the ability to adapt the flux at any time, in terms of both intensity and direction, according to the brightness requirements and specifics of the road pavement.

It is necessary for the road lighting community to obtain new reliable standard reference values representative of present-day pavement reflectance (q and r values) with assurance of traceability of measured data. For these reasons the EU Community funded the EMPIR SURFACE project^{14,15} with the goal to establish a metrological chain for the measurement of q and r values and to provide to the European standardization body new reference tables of q and r values for currently used pavements.

This deliverable first presents quantities and practices of road lighting with a focus on road photometry. In the next part, requirements for measuring instruments are presented as guidelines. Following, guidelines for measurement procedures are presented, first for laboratory and then for on-site measurements. The next part contains certain additional aspects to be considered. Finally, the suggestions and recommendations made by the SURFACE project is summarized.

2 QUANTITIES AND GEOMETRIES

2.1 Road surface measurement parameters

The methodology of photometrically characterising pavements was developed in the seventies¹⁶ and updated in 1982¹⁷ and 2001⁵. The quantities used in road lighting characterization are described in several reports from the International Commission on Illumination (CIE).^{2,18,19}

The surface of a pavement is classified according to its reflection properties. The reflectance is the ratio of the intensity of reflected radiation to that of the radiation incident to a surface. In road photometry, the most important characteristic parameter is the luminance coefficient q , given as:

$$q = \frac{L}{E} \quad (1)$$

It is the ratio between the luminance L in cd/m^2 , which the observer sees, and the illuminance E in lux which is incident on the surface. Since the eighties, for practical reasons, the luminance coefficient was replaced by the reduced luminance coefficient r in $\text{cd}/\text{m}^2/\text{lux}$, which is derived from q :

$$r = q \cos^3 \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

The standardised viewing height is 1.5 m and the angle of observation α is constant at 1° , corresponding to an observation distance of 86 m. In the standards concerning road lighting, the area of the road between 60 m and 160 m ahead of the driver is used, because it is considered an important area for the detection of obstacles. It was also defined for interurban driving where the speed is about 80 to 90 km/h. The observation angle $\alpha = 1^\circ$, is a convention, according to CIE 066 and CIE 144 guidelines and road lighting standards.

The luminance coefficient depends on the nature of the road surface material and on the positions of the light source and the observer relative to the element under consideration, as defined by the fixed angles α , and combination of the lighting angles β and ε , see Figure 1. A reduced coefficient table called r -table was defined, where the luminance coefficient r is given for a combination of fixed lighting angles β between 0 and 180° and $\tan \varepsilon$ between 0 and 12 . The luminance coefficient indicatrix also called reflexion indicatrix is a graphical representation of the r -table, which can be represented as De Boer 1967²⁰, see Figure 2, or projected in 2D, see Figure 3.

Figure 1. The photometric characteristics of the road surface depend on the angles of observation α , deviation β and incidence ϵ . By convention, according to CIE 066 and CIE 144 guidelines and road lighting standards, for the characterisation of road photometry, α is set at 1° .

Figure 2. Luminance coefficient indicatrix, presented by De Boer in 1967.

Figure 3. Projection in 2D of the reflection indicatrix.

The average luminance coefficient Q_0 , represents the degree of lightness of the measured surface⁵. It is computed as the average of the luminance coefficients over the specified solid angle, Ω_0 :

$$Q_0 = \frac{1}{\Omega_0} \int q \, d\Omega \quad (3)$$

In practice, due to the finite number of measurements, the integration results in a numerical summation approximated with weighting factors corresponding to the solid angle attributed to each value $\Delta\omega$ and given for each combination of $\tan \varepsilon$ and β angles.²

$$Q_0 = \frac{\sum q \cdot \Delta\omega}{\sum \Delta\omega} \quad (4)$$

The specular factor S_1 represents the degree of specularity (shininess) of the observed surface. It is defined as the ratio between the reduced luminance coefficients of two specific illumination conditions:

$$S_1 = \frac{r(\beta=0, \tan \varepsilon=2)}{r(\beta=0, \tan \varepsilon=0)} \quad (5)$$

2.2 Measurement geometries according to CIE and Standards requirements

The geometry currently used with an observation angle of 1° for the design of pavement lighting was defined in the nineteen-seventies and confirmed in 1982¹⁷, 2001⁵, and 2019¹⁹. In these CIE documents and in the road lighting standard EN 13201-3⁴, the height of the eye of the observer is set at the nominal value of 1.5 m. In the same standard, the range of observation angle is conventionally assumed to be $1.0 \pm 0.5^\circ$ according to a viewing distance between 60 and 160 m.

Concerning the characterization of road markings, other geometries are defined in the standard EN 1436²¹. The eye of the observer is set at the nominal value of 1.2 m and the angle of observation is 2.29° , which corresponds to a distance of observation of 30 m. In the road marking standard, the tolerance on the observation angle is $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The coefficient of retroreflected luminance R_L corresponds to the night visibility of the marking, with an illumination angle of 1.24° (Figure 4a).

The luminance coefficient under diffuse illumination Q_d (Equation 6), was developed for road markings but could be also relevant for road surfaces^{5,21}. Q_d is defined as the quotient of reflected luminance at 2.29° under diffuse illumination (Figure 4b). It is the average of the luminance coefficient weighted by $\cos \varepsilon$ integrated over the complete hemisphere above the road surface.

$$Q_d = \frac{\int q \cos \varepsilon \, d\Omega}{\int \cos \varepsilon \, d\Omega} \quad (6)$$

Figure 4. Schematic representations of the conventional geometry for the photometric characterisation of road markings according to EN 1436, which defines a nominal observation angle of 2.29° corresponding to an observation distance of 30 m and a driver's eye height of 1.2 m. a. Geometry for the measurement of the retroreflection factor R_L : the illumination angle is set to 1.24° . b. Geometry of the measurement of the luminance coefficient under diffuse illumination Q_d . The integrating sphere creates a diffuse illumination from the light source placed in the middle of the sphere.

In the nineteen-nineties, Sorensen²² suggested using Q_d instead of Q_0 for road lighting specification. At that time, both were measured at a nominal observation angle of 1° . A method to compute Q_d from an r -table was given²². A device able to measure Q_d and Q_0 was developed²² having an observation angle of 1.37° . The calculation of the average luminance and illuminance ratio in a typical lighting installation with two different lamp settings for the standard r -tables defined in CIE 066² was compared²³ to the values of Q_d and Q_0 . For the two road lighting installations used, Q_d gave the best estimate of the average luminance with discrepancies between 0 % and ± 8 % for Q_d and an underestimation with Q_0 from -12 % to -39 %. Brusque and Carta²⁴ made the same comparison with 12 lighting installations and the measured r -tables of 164 different pavements from R1 to R4: The mean discrepancy was between -2 % and -13 % for Q_0 and between -13 % and -41 % for Q_d . The results obtained were always better when using Q_0 and showed that the Q_d factor underestimates the specular effect and that differences are larger for grazing angles.

After these studies, the CIE 144⁵ confirmed the observation angle of 1° and the use of Q_0 for pavement characterisation and an observation angle of 2.29° for road markings.

Gibbons²⁵ used a four-angle gonioreflectometer to study the influence of different observation angles on 20 core pavements with $\alpha = 1^\circ, 2^\circ, 3^\circ, 5^\circ, 7^\circ, 10^\circ, 12^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 90° . It was shown that the lightness of the pavement changes with the observation angle and that, except for the smaller observation angles, the specularity decreases with the observation angle.

In more recent literature, a suggestion of different observation angles was made by Chain.²⁶ These were 90° for the characterisation of light from airplanes, 3° for urban applications, 10° for cyclists and pedestrians and 45° for visually impaired people. For visually impaired people, the observation angle is set at 45° in the standard concerning pedotactile caution warning devices²⁷. The eye of the observer is also set by convention at 1.5 m.

Some oculometric studies^{28,29} show differences in visual strategy of cyclists as a function of age, but none of them propose a preponderant angle of observation. Patla and Vickers³⁰ have shown that when a walker is required to step on specific locations in the travel path during locomotion, he looks on average two steps ahead. This result was confirmed by Fotios and Uttley³¹ who found using eye tracking that obstacles are detected approximately 3.4 m ahead, thus corresponding to an observation angle of 27° if the eye is at a height of 1.5 m.

Stockmar³² also suggested an angle of 3°, more adapted to urban applications. In his study, he indicates that the use of an observation angle of 3° instead of 1° induces a 10 % reduction of Q_0 . Sorensen³³ has developed a device able to measure at 1°, 1.5° and 2.29°. The first results on a class R2 pavement show that the impact on Q_0 and S_1 is weak, especially for Q_0 (and Q_d). The specular factor S_1 drops with increasing angle.

In the Greffier case study,³⁴ the impact of using observation angles of 2.29°, 3°, and 5° was studied with a mobile luminance camera. The luminance and uniformities were calculated according to the EN 13201 mesh grid, using the concept of a mobile observer proposed by Stockmar³². The first results show that the luminance decreases with an increase of the observation angle, see Figure 5.

a)

b)

Figure 5. a) Example of a luminance image taken with a luminance camera. The areas corresponding to different angles of observation are shown. b) Corresponding luminance measured with the concept of a moving observer.

2.2.1 Impact on lighting pollution

Concerning the impact of light pollution on astronomical observation, no specific angle is given in the CIE document⁵. However, according to the experience of astronomers,³⁵⁻³⁷ the artificial sky luminance is mainly generated by the luminous flux, emitted directly by the luminaires and reflected by the illuminated surfaces, within the range of elevation between 0° and 20° over the horizontal plane. At such elevations, the light travels in the low levels of the atmosphere, where the aerosols generate downward diffusion into the entrance pupil of a telescope and a sort of veiling luminance in the star observation direction. This reduces the contrast of the heavenly bodies since it adds to the natural sky luminance. Upward light with elevations higher than 20° travels in higher layers of the atmosphere, where aerosols are not present, and generates a much lower downward diffusion.

A town can be treated as a single uniformly diffusing source³⁸; most luminaires are hidden in cavities between buildings and few luminaires are not screened by buildings (typically on the boundary of the town or in large open areas). The road surface behaviour for light pollution is similar: light reflected by road at angles between 0° and 20° over the horizontal road plane have higher impact on astronomical observations too (Figure 6). Unfortunately, these angles are very close to the lighting angles (up to 70° to 75° from the vertical) that provide lighting efficiency. Furthermore, to reach these grazing angles using discharge lamp sources entails some

upward direct light (about 2 to 3%) from the luminaires. Only certain LED luminaires satisfy standard specifications on zero upward flux. But one shall keep in mind that light pollution and energy consumption are related to the illuminance on the road,^{39,40} while visibility and safety are directly linked to the luminance measured along the observation direction.

In calculations of obtrusive light and in particular for the calculation of the upward flux ratio⁴¹, the reflectance of the road is the ratio between the incident illuminance and the reflected illuminance measured at one meter height⁴². It should be mentioned that examples of different surface reflectance are based on measurements done in the nineties and have not been updated since then.

Figure 6. Theoretical model for light pollution evaluation of the light emission of town.

2.3 SURFACE project analysis of geometries

Concerning the illumination angles, there is a need for more data at grazing angles due to the use of guide lighting devices mounted at low heights, especially in tunnels. Since the r -table is only defined up to $\tan \epsilon = 12$, when the mounting height of the luminaires is very low ($H < 2$ m), an extension for $\tan \epsilon$ is needed. For this reason, in EN 13201-3⁴ the informative annex B defines an extended r -table format for luminaires with low mounting height. The r -table is extended in $\tan \epsilon$ up to 20, by increment of 0.5 for every β angle. However, there is still a need for such data and a new calculation of Q_0 should be proposed to take this table into account. However, up to now, it seems that nobody is able to make measurements at such grazing angles. The main reason is the required very small angular subtense of both the detector and the source.

Concerning the observation angle, it is affected by both the vehicle type and the distance of observation. For drivers of motorized vehicles, in the EN 13201 standards, the main lighting criteria for interurban driving are based on the road surface luminance and include the average luminance, the overall uniformity and the longitudinal uniformity. The driver's eye is assumed to be at the nominal height of 1.5 m above the road surface and the angle of observation is fixed to 1° below the horizontal, corresponding to a distance of 86 m ahead of the observer. This geometry is well adapted for a speed of 90 km/h, on motorways for example. However, nowadays, except in tunnels, there are few interurban lighted roads in Europe. Illuminated areas are located in urban environments where there are several types of road users (vehicle drivers, but also cyclists and pedestrians), travelling at different speeds. To define new observation angles, a first approach is to consider the stopping distance, which is a summation of the reaction distance and braking distance. Typical stopping

distances in Europe are presented in Table 1. For road safety, good visibility of obstacles within the stopping distance is very important.

Table 1. Stopping distance at different driving speeds (according to the authors' country driving code).

Speed (km/h)		Stopping distance on dry pavement in official documents (m)			
		France ⁴³	Italy ⁴⁴	Sweden ⁴⁵	Switzerland ⁴⁶
Urban driving	30	13	22	16	16 - 22
	50	28	55	38	34 - 48
Interurban driving	90	70	136	121	88 - 115
	120	112	235	222	144 - 189

Concerning the height of the observer, the SURFACE proposal is to keep the height of the observer at the nominal value of 1.5 m, in order to be consistent with EN 13201 and the CIE recommendation. This height is adequate for drivers, cyclists, and pedestrians. In Table 2, the corresponding distance is computed for different observation angles. There is no impact for existing road surface and marking measuring devices because they consider a measuring angle, not a height, expressed as a nominal value⁴⁷.

Table 2. Distances which correspond to different nominal observation angles at 1.5-m height of observer.

Observation angle α (°)	1	2.29	3	5	7	10	20	45
Corresponding viewing distance (m)	85.9	37.5	28.6	17.1	12.2	8.5	4.1	1.5

Table 3. SURFACE recommendation for new geometries.

Road environment condition	Nominal observation angle recommendation
Extra-urban road	1°, viewing distance of 85.9 m
Urban road	2.29°, viewing distance of 37.5 m

Based on standards and our bibliography, the SURFACE consortium recommends in Table 3 different nominal observation angles for different driving conditions and road users: for urban environment 2.29° (consistent with road marking standards and stopping distances in urban environment), for extra-urban environment 1° (consistent with previous geometries). The angle of 5°, corresponding to a viewing distance of 17 m, is an interesting complement, suitable for urban driving at low speed, cycling and for scooters. The angles of 10° and 20° are under consideration for describing the boundary between diffuse and specular behaviour.

To improve astronomic observations, a reduction of the prescribed values of road illuminance, and for zones close to observatories also of the luminance value, is required. But the safety of road users must be ensured by alternative means and strategies, like higher lighting levels at intersections and on pedestrian crossings, very low mounting-height luminaires and new visibility models.

As shown in Ref. 48, some measurement devices are already able to measure at the new angles of observation and some are under development within the SURFACE consortium. Using lower grazing angles has several

---	-------------------------	----------------------	--------------------	---

advantages because the design tolerance on the angles is less critical, and thus it is possible to construct more compact instruments. Moreover, existing devices used for the characterisation of road marking could also be transformed to measure road surface photometry. Therefore, these new geometries allow the development of less expensive measurement devices and an increased accuracy also for on-site verification.

3 GUIDELINES ON METROLOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR PORTABLE AND LABORATORY INSTRUMENTS

3.1 Metrological requirements of laboratory instruments

Laboratory instruments should be able to measure the parameters mentioned above, under the geometry specified by the norms. New measurement geometries are also suggested and can therefore become part of the requirements. All the combinations of angles presented in the *r*-table need to be measured.

There are additional combinations of angles in the so-called *extended r*-table where $\tan \varepsilon$ is extended up to 20, by increment of 0.5. However, up to now, it seems that no measurement device is able to make measurements at such grazing angles. The main reason is the required very small angular subtense of both the detector and the source that are not currently implemented in devices for *r*-table measurements and only very few devices for BRDF satisfy these conditions.

3.2 Measurement parameters and geometries

The strict definition of the luminance coefficients (and of the BRDF) implies that the illuminance is measured at a given point (i.e. within an infinitesimal small area) and the luminance at the same point, in a given direction (i.e. within an infinitesimal small solid angle). In addition, the incident light should originate from a given direction (i.e. a source with infinitesimal solid angle). In practice, this is not possible as finite apertures are necessary to emit and collect light. Furthermore, road surfaces are highly non-uniform, hence the luminance coefficient will vary at each point and averages over a certain surface area need to be taken. It is recommended to measure an area not less than 100 cm². This ensures that the measurement is representative of the surface as a whole. It means that the measurement is averaged over enough points, and the result should be similar if the measurement is done on another part of the road.

The direct application of the definition of luminance coefficient implies that luminance is measured with a luminance meter, an imaging luminance measurement device (ILMD), or a similar setup which limits the field-of-view of the detector. In this configuration, the illuminated surface is usually larger than the measurement surface, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. A schematic of a measurement setup. The field of view is limiting the measured area.

The limitation of the field of view can also be made by limiting the illumination field. In this configuration, the illuminated field is smaller than the actual field-of-view of the detector, see Figure 8.

Figure 8. A schematic of a measurement setup. The illumination determines the measured area.

Due to the finite apertures and illuminated area, the measurement system therefore suffers from different (systematic) effects, including:

1. In a perfect case, the illuminance field is perfectly homogenous, and no light is outside the nominal field. In practice the illumination field is not homogenous, i.e. $E = E(x, y)$
2. The incidence angles (β, ε) on the illumination field vary inside the illumination field $(\beta, \varepsilon) = (\beta(x, y), \varepsilon(x, y))$.

Both effects are represented schematically in Figure 9.

Figure 9. A schematic of the non-uniformity of the illumination, both angularly and spatially.

Due to the size of the source, not only the nominal incidence angles will reach the point but a whole set of angles $(\beta, \varepsilon) = (\beta(x, y, x_s, y_s), \varepsilon(x, y, x_s, y_s))$ as shown in Figure 10. The set of angles reaching the surface should be smaller than the smallest separation between illumination angles required for the measurement. It is about 0.2° in ε and 2° in β for the standard r -table. A larger value will "blur" the results and two neighbouring measurements will be correlated. This can be ensured by a good collimation of the source and by a small angular subtense of the source. In order to measure a large enough area while respecting this requirement, large distances are needed between the source and the sample.

Similar considerations are valid for the detector part, i.e. the detection angles varies across the detection field and the input aperture of the detectors, $(\alpha, \delta) = (\alpha(x, y, x_D, y_D), \delta(x, y, x_D, y_D))$, as shown in the schematic in Figure 11.

Figure 10. A schematic of the effect due to the angular subtense of the source. A point of the illuminated surface receives light from different parts of the source.

Figure 11. A schematic of the angular subtense of the detector. The detector sees a point of the surface within a range of angles.

Due to these different effects, an aperture factor k_A can be determined for all measurement geometries $(\alpha, \epsilon, \beta)$. The factor is the ratio between the measurement with aperture effect, L_D and the measurement without aperture effect, L_0 :

$$k_A(\alpha, \epsilon, \beta) = \frac{L_0}{L_D}$$

It is therefore important to control the geometry of a given setup to make sure it complies with the requirements or to include this effect in the uncertainty evaluation.

3.2.1 Measurement conditions and parameters contributing to the uncertainty

A very important aspect of the measurement procedure is to identify the different factors affecting the measurement and contributing to the uncertainty. Ideally, those effects should be minimized as much as possible, but the remaining contributions should be evaluated. A list of the measurement quantities and calibration factor identified are presented in Table 4 and the measurement errors in Table 5. The same factors are present for *in-situ* and laboratory measurements, but most of them can be better controlled during laboratory measurements. SURFACE consortium has developed a dedicated software for the evaluation of luminance coefficient measurement uncertainty.

Table 4. Measurement quantities and calibration factors.

q_T	Output quantity: luminance coefficient at a nominal direction of illumination (β, ε)
$s_{L,T}$	Signal of the (luminance) detector when measuring a test surface
$s_{L0,T}$	Dark signal of the (luminance) detector when measuring a test surface
$s_{E,T}$	Signal of the illuminance detector
$s_{E0,T}$	Dark signal of the illuminance detector
k_E	Calibration factor of the illuminance meter (unit: signal · lx ⁻¹)
k_L	Calibration factor of the luminance meter (unit: signal · [cd/m ²] ⁻¹)

Table 5. Measurement uncertainty contributions.

$k_A(\beta, \varepsilon)$	Aperture effect (see section 3.2)
α_L	Temperature coefficient of luminance meter (unit: K ⁻¹)
α_E	Temperature coefficient of illuminance meter (unit: K ⁻¹)
ΔT_T	Temperature difference between calibration of illuminance/luminance meter and the measurement
$a_\alpha(\alpha)$	Angular error in α – q error contribution due to error on α : depends also on the sample reflexion characteristic, geometric effect
$a_\beta(\beta)$	Angular error in β – idem
$a_\varepsilon(\varepsilon)$	Angular error in ε – idem
$a_E(\varepsilon)$	Cosine mismatch of the illuminance meter
$a_a(\varphi, \phi)$	Error due to the tilt of the measured surface in respect to the coordinate system of the measurement device
o_{lin}	Nonlinearity
o_{stray}	Straylight <u>Two cases:</u> Goniometer in lab: stray light comes from the instrument light source Portable Goniometer: stray light comes from the instrument light source and the external environment (can be minimized if the light source is modulated)
o_{vlam}	$V(\lambda)$ mismatch <u>As the output quantity is a ratio of photometric quantities:</u> To be considered: the difference of light source calibration spectrum and instrument light source spectrum, nevertheless a significant mismatch for both illuminance meter and luminance meter could exist, but if all light sources are the same type (e.g. III A for calibration and instrument) the error will be negligible given the neutrality of the samples.

Table 5. Measurement uncertainty contributions.

	<p>If it is not the case, to be considered: the differences of spectral sensitivity between illuminance and luminance meter weighted by the instrument light source spectrum.</p> <p>Also the difference of the transfer of the photometric scale is not considered as it is a ratio of two photometric quantities supposedly calibrated with the same scale.</p>
	<p>Lamp instability (contribution depends on the measurement process and environmental conditions)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Drift, which has been determined and therefore can be corrected b) Fluctuations, which have been observed, but cannot be corrected and therefore should be taken into account as a contribution to uncertainty
	<p>Illuminance nonuniformity (contribution depends on the way the illuminance is measured)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Drift, which has been determined and therefore can be corrected b) Fluctuations, which have been observed, but cannot be corrected and therefore should be taken into account as a contribution to uncertainty
	<p>Luminance meter characteristics (excluding linearity):</p> <p>Contribution relative to the difference between calibration conditions and measurement conditions (source size effect, ...)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Drift, which has been determined and therefore can be corrected b) Fluctuations, which have been observed, but cannot be corrected and therefore should be taken into account as a contribution to uncertainty
	<p>Overlap between detection field and illumination field:</p> <p>This is normally a problem which is handled in the instrument design, but if not done perfectly, it may produce drift or fluctuation.</p>

3.2.2 Summary of the metrological requirements to measure *r*-tables

Table 5 lists the recommended requirements.

Table 6. Requirements for optimal laboratory measurement conditions.

Property	Value
A measurement geometry that corresponds to the norm (observation angle)	1°, 2.29°
A measure that is representative of the surface (i.e. an average over enough points)	100 cm ²
Good collimation, i.e. small angular subtense of the light source	<0.2°
Small detector angular subtense, i.e. good telecentricity of the detector	<0.08° cf CIE 66 ²
Good calibration of the different elements	
Determination of the values of the relevant parameters contributing to the uncertainty	

4 GUIDELINES FOR LABORATORY MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES

4.1 Sample preparation and marking

4.1.1 General information

The sample can be extracted from the road or prepared in laboratory. In both cases, attention needs to be paid not to change the surface to be measured. Dust, water, etc, should be avoided from the confection of extraction until measurement. It is important to know with which device the sample will be tested in order to provide adequate sample dimensions. Usually, tested surface dimensions and sample height have to be within a specific range, and it can be quite difficult to adjust after extraction.

It is up to the testing laboratory to refuse a sample if the sample surface is deemed to be compromised by dirt and/or debris.

The test direction must be clearly indicated on the sample. As the measured surface should not be altered (for example by glue or marker as shown in Figure 13, the marking needs to be done either on the back or on the sides of the sample. In case of side marking, it should be an arrow oriented from the bottom of the sample to the observed surface, as shown in Figure 12. The measurement device must aim at the arrow pointing upwards.

Figure 12. An example of the marking of the measured surface of a sample.

The identification of the sample should also be written either on the side or on the back, for subsequent referencing.

4.1.2 Road extraction

In the case of road extraction, the position of the measurement should be carefully referenced. The general localisation is the name of the road or street and the direction of circulation. In tunnels, a more precise localisation can be easily done by the use of the different markings of the length of the tunnel. In roads it could be either geographical coordinates, a distance in the road reference system, or a distance to a visible fixed object like for example a traffic sign. The lateral positioning is also important. The lane number if it is a multi-lane road and to indicate if the sample was extracted in the tyre track, in the centre of the lane or somewhere else (shoulder for example).

Avoid evident heterogenous area (non-planar, stain or dust, etc.) in the sampling area. It is necessary to use a sampling procedure which avoids introducing dirt and debris. If this happens the sample should be cleaned on site.

The test direction should be the circulation direction, so this has to be clearly indicated on the sample with an arrow. It is possible to mark the surface to be measured with a tape before extraction and then indicate the

viewing direction on the back and remove the tape as soon as the sample is extracted. This is useful as the extraction often turns the sample around.

Figure 13. An example of the marking of the observation direction of a sample. The tape should not be left on the measured surface as it may alter the surface of the sample. The indication of the observation direction and the name of the sample should be put on the backside or on the sides.

During the extraction procedure, care must be taken to prevent the samples from getting dirty. If dirt is introduced, samples should be cleaned with water (at medium pressure) on site before the mud from the extraction action dries.

4.1.3 Laboratory confection

Depending on how the sample was made, this direction have to be carefully chosen: for example asphalt slab are often compacted with a wheel and hence the wheel direction must be the tested direction. However, with a gyratory compression, any direction can be chosen. It is important to avoid dust, sand, or filler contact with freshly made asphalt concrete samples in order to prevent any particle to stick on the non-dry binder (bitumen or another material). Indeed, these particles would be impossible to remove once the binder drought and it can alter the observed surface colour or aspect.

4.1.4 Transport and storage

During transport and storage before and/or after measurement, samples must be placed in conditions that cannot alter it and in particular the observed surface. For transport, samples must be covered with carton or some protective material, in order to prevent any direct contact with the observed surface. If the sample has asphalt binder, a protection around the lateral boundaries is also recommended.

For a storage period, it is also important to protect the observed surface, however the cover must also block sunlight as it can alter it with time.

For storage it is suggested to store the samples indoor, preferably in a controlled temperature room. If this is not available, it should be stored not exposed to direct sunlight, upside down and covered.

4.2 Setup alignment

The different parts that need to be aligned are directly determined by the measurement geometries. The alignment needs to ensure that the positioning of the source, sample and detector are correct with regards to each other. The centre of the measurement needs to be defined. This corresponds to the measurement point P in Figure 1. The source, sample and detector can then be aligned in relation to this point. The observation angle is fixed throughout the measurement. The sample and the detector need to be aligned in a way that

there is as small error as possible on the observation angle, as well as on the illumination angle. The angular subtense of the detector and of the illumination, should be known.

Typically, a laser can be used to align the different parts. It allows the user to define principal axis, the reference plane and can be used determine the angular positioning of the different elements. The surface of the sample should be placed in the reference plane, corresponding to the measured plane.

4.3 Measurement methods

There are basically two approaches to measure the luminance coefficient. The calibration procedure depends on which one of the two methods is used:

4.3.1 Absolute method

The definition of the luminance coefficient is directly applied. Thus, the luminance coefficient of a test surface $q_T = \frac{L}{E}$. In terms of measured signals

$$q_T = \frac{s_{L,T}}{s_{E,T}} \cdot \frac{k_E}{k_L}, \quad (1) \text{ where } s_{L,T} \text{ is the signal measured by the luminance}$$

detector when measuring the test surface, $s_{E,T}$ is the signal of the illuminance detector, k_E is the sensitivity of the illuminance detector obtained by calibration, and k_L is the sensitivity of the luminance detector obtained by calibration. In this case, the luminance and illuminance detector each need to be calibrated separately, following a standard procedure. It could be noted here that the illuminance can be measured once, for normal incidence, and then deduced for other incidence angles applying the $\cos(\epsilon)$ law and optionally monitoring the light source.

4.3.2 Relative method

A reflection standard is used to calibrate the system. In addition, often an additional detector is used to monitor the signal of the source:

$$q_T = q_R \frac{s_{L,T}}{s_{L,R}} \cdot \frac{s_{M,R}}{s_{M,T}}, \quad (2)$$

where $s_{L,T}$ is the signal of the (luminance) detector when measuring the test surface, $s_{L,R}$ is the signal of the (luminance) detector when measuring the reference surface, $s_{M,R}$ is the signal of the monitor detector of the source when measuring the reference surface, $s_{M,T}$ is the signal of the monitor detector of the source when measuring the test surface, and q_R is the luminance coefficient of the reference surface. In this case, the reference surface needs to be measured by an accredited laboratory. The linearity of the detector also needs to be known through calibration.

Ideally, multiple measurements of the same sample should be made. Obviously, the feasibility depends a lot on the time needed for one measurement. It is recommended to measure at least twice. It is also recommended to start the measurement with a standard plate to ensure that the alignment of the setup and the measurement conditions are normal.

4.4 Measurement conditions

The measurements conditions should be documented, in particular:

- Regarding the sample: Sample identification code and date of extraction, condition of storage, washing

- Regarding the laboratory environment: environmental conditions including temperature and humidity, any other relevant conditions including lamp control. Depending on the type of light source used, it should be warmed-up to ensure a better stability.
- Regarding the measuring device: time of switch-on of the device (including lamp) and time of start and end of measurement, and if used, reference material used for initial setup

5 GUIDELINES FOR ON-SITE MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES

5.1 Road site definition – measurement conditions

Figure 14. Typical multilane divided roadway. Sampling sites or measurement sites should be identified with reference to lane, tyre track or centre, driving direction, etc.

Figure 14 shows a typical road site with indications of the necessary information to be recorded when performing measurement or taking samples.

5.2 Road condition – selection of the measurement area

Since 1° is a very grazing angle, the area of measurement shall be planar and without defects like cracks or special spots.

5.3 Measurement conditions

The road must be accessible and not used by vehicles at the time of measurement.

The pavement must be dry, unsalted and the outside temperature above $+5^\circ\text{C}$ because at lower temperature, the humidity may condense on the road, and the electronics may not behave as expected. In the presence of salt or dust, the photometry could be different, so it is always better to make measurements on a clean road.

The measurement shall be done in the direction of circulation. The photometry of the road is affected by the traffic as illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 15. General view of a road pavement where tyre tracks within lanes are visible.

If possible, the measurements should be done on each lane of circulation, in the centre and in the tyre tracks. One shall consider the tyre tracks in the data analysis.

The effect of traffic, time and dust are illustrated in section 6.1.

5.3.1 Measurement area selection

A specific contour gauge for on-site selection of measurement areas has been designed to account for surface discrepancies on measurement angles on site, see Figure 16. It is a gauge built by a frame (equipped with adjustable stands) which keeps tightly against one another parallel and in the same plane a set of plastic (or metal) needles, each 2-cm wide. The total length of the frame should be at least 50 cm or slightly larger than the maximum size of the measuring device. Each needle can move independently following the profile and roughness of the road, see Figure 16 b). Usually, contour gauges are available on the market and used to draw the profile of objects and surfaces but have small needles, providing higher accuracy in the contour draw. For the purpose of measurement area selection, larger needles are needed: a needle width of 2 cm ensures to neglect road variations due to irregularities of hard elements like stones, but allows the detection of larger planarity distortions (concave surface) that can influence measurement geometry.

The contour gauge can easily be 3D printed.

Figure 16. Contour gauge for the identification of road surface irregularities: a) dimensions, b) simulation on site

Choose places where the pavement seems clean. If it is not, state that it is a special characterization (impact of rubber for example).

5.3.2 Common practices concerning the number of measurements

As stated before, the advantage of a portable reflectometer is that it is able to make several measurements without damaging the road, and thus they are more representative of its actual photometry. The question raised is: what is the number of necessary measurements and where shall they be taken?

In the literature, there is not a lot of recommendations on the number of measurements. Ref. 49 makes 10 measurements: 5 in the centre track and 5 in the tyre track. In Ref. 50, to characterise a site, they measure 5 points in the centre with a spacing of 1 m. Ref. 47 makes 3 to 4 transversal profiles and in each profile makes a measurement in the right tyre track and the centre track. To enable later measurements at the same place, they also note the position of each photometric measurement (lateral distance to the right road marking and longitudinal distance with fixed objects like a road sign or mileage point).

The same approach is used by Cerema as illustrated in Figure 17 and Figure 18.

Figure 17. a) An example of position marking in a Swiss tunnel. The exact measurement location can be retrieved from the plan of the tunnel and the number (here N5:430:050). b) Example of measurement of lateral position relative to a marking.

Figure 18 : Example of precise localisation of measurements points. In the picture, the words “lane” or “line” is used instead of “track”.

A. Ekrias⁵², communication at Surface stakeholder meeting in Washington 2019, does 6 measurements: 3 in the centre track and 3 in the tyre track. Corell³³ measures in 6 points, 3 on the tyre track and three on the centre track.

Ref. 53 made in this way; “On the road in question five small areas are indicated across each driving lane; the two tyre tracks, the oil track in between, and the areas to the left (the road centre) and the left (the kerb side). In each small areas 10 measurements are made in short succession by just shifting the device over several cm. To be able to characterize the road as a whole, this is repeated at least 8 times over a length of about 100 m. So, in each direction the reflection is measured at least 80 times.”

To study the impact of the number of measurements, Ref. 54 performed an experiment. On 6 sites, they did measurements at 2 positions, and at 4 positions in another site. The outcome of the experiment is however unclear.

For specific studies where regular measurements are taken (studying age and traffic effect for example), it is useful to measure the longitudinal position of the measurement (taken from something visible like a lamp or a traffic sign) and the distance between the right marking lane and the place of measurement. This is particularly important if a pavement sample shall be subsequently extracted from the same place. A proposal is to make half of the measurements on the road centre track and half on the right tyre track for security reason (left tyre track in countries with left-hand side driving).

METAS measures each lane 3 times. One measurement is made in each tyre track and one in the centre track. The device allows the measurement of S_1 and Q_0 but not of the complete r -table. The average is done for each lane and for all the lanes measured. The resulting averaged S_1 and Q_0 are reported to the clients.

SURFACE proposal

The key point concerns the selection of the measurement area:

- SURFACE recommends choosing several sampling areas and perform at least 6 measurements:
 - o 3 in the tyre track and 3 on the centre track.
 - o If it is possible to make more measurements, it is better.
 - o The advice is to make the same number of measurements in the tyre track and in the centre track.

Six measurements seem to be the minimum required to be representative of the road heterogeneity and to enable statistics. It is always possible to make characterisation at specific area, but it shall be noted.

5.3.3 Description of the measurements

General information shall be given to describe as much as possible:

- the place and conditions of measurement: type of road and its use, traffic, date, meteorological conditions (e.g. cloudy, sunny, windy, etc.), environmental conditions, including temperature, humidity and dew point if available
- the type of pavement describing its general aspects (Is it dirty? Are the tyre tracks visible?) and all available information as its age, size and colour of the granulate, type of binder, special surface treatment, etc.
- pictures with a general view and more close-up view with a pencil or a grid to provide a size and a colour scale, including a picture with the contour gauge

Figure 19. Close-up views of different pavements before measurement with a portable device. An object or a ruler is used to provide a scale and an idea of the colour of the pavement.

5.4 Data analysis

SURFACE suggests some general warnings are needed to explain the representativeness of measured data.

The measured values depend on: *heterogeneity of the surface along the road length because of the construction process and the weather exposure, type of asphalt and binder, traffic, usage, ageing, and on the measured place (centre track or tyre track).*

All these factors may strongly affect the measured data, which may not be representative of the sample (i.e. do not belong to the same statistical population). This directly impacts the representativeness of the mean.

For all the above reasons there are several possible approaches to provide the measured on-site *r*-tables of several measuring points.

SURFACE recommends to:

- *avoid a mean value of an r-table because it may not be representative of a physical surface*
- *provide the most representative r-tables (considering the shape of the solid) and the extremes, i.e. three values*
- *for devices measuring only Q_0 and S_1 , provide the mean value and standard deviation*

5.4.1 Specific approach for on-site measurements data analysis

On-site measurements are usually done on several points on the road and the data analysis involves a large number of measurements. For these reasons SURFACE suggests a specific approach on the analysis.

Concerning the analysis, several approaches are possible:

- A. Calculate the mean of all measurements and the standard deviation to quantify the road heterogeneity
- B. Differentiate the statistics for the centre track and tyre track: calculate the average and standard deviation for each
- C. Calculate a weighted average: Make a ponderation between measurement on the centre track and tyre track with a weight of 2/3 on the centre track and 1/3 on the tyre track to represent the percentage of each case on the road
- D. Choose an *r*-table which is representative of all the measurements. This last approach has the advantage of the choice of a real physical table instead of an artificial table done with the mean of all the *r* factors (mathematically incorrect because a weighted average is done to calculate Q_0).

In the literature, Jackett⁴⁹ and Ekrias⁵² average their measures. For its clients, Muzet⁵¹ usually select the most representative table, calculates standard deviations and sometimes provides extreme tables.

SURFACE recommends the following key points concerning the use of the data:

- *If the classical lighting design approach is used (one typical CIE r-table with a scaling of Q_0), the measured r-table is not used but only Q_0 and S_1 factors. Thus, the average of the measured Q_0 , S_1 factors could be used, using one of the preceding approaches (A, B or C). As in CIE144, the average of S_1 is used to choose the typical table and the average of Q_0 will add the scaling factor. To characterise the heterogeneity of the road, provide the mean value and also the standard deviation.*
- *If the actual r-table of the pavement could be used in the lighting design, it is recommended to choose a representative measured r-table instead of an average (approach D). It will provide a more physically realistic BRDF. This table is the closest from the average of the S_1 factor, makes physical sense and could be scaled according to the average of the Q_0 factor. To characterise the heterogeneity of the road, provide the mean value and also the extremes.*

6 GUIDELINES FOR CONSIDERING ADDITIONAL ASPECTS

6.1 State of the pavement considering dirt, and impact of traffic

The effects of time and traffic density can be studied with portable devices. On the slow lane, dedicated to trucks, the aspects could be different because it has the heaviest traffic. Thus, if possible, the measurements should be done on each lane of circulation, in the centre track and in the tyre track. One shall consider the tyre track in the data analysis.

Figure 20 and Figure 21 illustrate the effect of time and traffic for a concrete⁵⁵ and a bituminous pavement⁵¹.

Figure 20. Illustration of the heterogeneity of the photometry of cement concrete pavements. The photometric measurements were done with Coluroute portable device on the new pavements (T0 in red), after 6 months (in yellow), 18 months (in green) and 30 months (in blue). The centre track measurements are represented by triangles and the tyre track measurements by circles⁵⁵. In the graph legend, the word “lane” is used instead of “track”.

Figure 21. Illustration of the age and traffic effect on a circulated typical French pavement whose photometry was measured every 6 months during 3 years with Coluroute portable device⁵¹. The centre track measurements are represented by triangles and the tyre track measurements by circles. In the graph legend, the word “lane” is used instead of “track”.

In these two cases, the centre track is slightly darker and less specular than the tyre track.

The effect of ambient conditions without traffic was seldom studied and it is always difficult to isolate the effect of traffic from the time and ambient conditions.

In Fotios⁷ analysis of Cooper 2000 measurement campaign in the UK, samples were extracted on 83 places with 3 samples in each place: one in the near side (supposed as non-circulated), one in the tyre track and one in the “oil” track (supposed as in the centre track). The results were averaged by pavement type and no effect of traffic, nor “dust” was found.

A huge campaign of on-site measurements were done across New Zealand with the Memphis portable device⁵⁶. There were 140 representative sites measured in autumn 2008. For each site, five measurements were taken on the shoulder (no vehicle circulation) and five on the tyre track. With this study, the effect of traffic could be studied because there is no vehicle circulation on the shoulder where half of the measurements were done.

Figure 22. Positions of the ten measurements for each site. From Ref. 49.

The pavements measured were always more than 1 year old and more than 2 years old in 92 % of the cases. There were continuous asphalt concrete, porous asphalt (called OGPA), and also surface dressing pavements (called chipseal). The effect of traffic is represented in Figure 23 for asphalt concrete (a) and surface dressing (b). It shows in both cases that Q_0 and S_1 are bigger in the circulated part of the road. Considering each site, the specularity of the shoulder is considerably lower than the circulated part and the pavement is darker. The authors conclude that “both Q_0 and S_1 increase with traffic wear in somewhat similar proportions”.

Figure 23. Q_0 and S_1 for asphalt concrete (AC for asphalt concrete and OGPA for open graded porous asphalt) surfaces in a) and for chipseal surfaces (surface dressing) in b). The arrow shows the direction of movement from shoulder to tyre track (solid circle = shoulder value, arrowhead = tyre track value). From Ref. 49.

This effect is not so important when centre tracks and tyre tracks are compared, but is still valid.

In the presence of salt or dust, the specularity is generally lower, as illustrated in Figure 20.

6.2 Tolerances and uncertainties

The luminance coefficient is the quantity used to design road lighting system able to satisfy normative requirements in terms of provided road luminance. European standards models the road surface as a horizontal plane lighted only by the luminaires of the road lighting installation. For our purpose the original formula that gives the luminance at a point p of the road surface, can be rewritten, considering only one luminaire, as:

$$L = \frac{I(C, \gamma) r(\tan \epsilon, \beta) f_M}{H^2} = \frac{I_n(C, \gamma) \Phi r(\tan \epsilon, \beta) f_M}{H^2}$$

Where, with reference to geometry of Figure 1:

L	is the luminance at the point p , in candelas per square metre;
$I(C, \gamma)$	is the luminous intensity of the luminaire at direction specified by angular coordinates (C, γ) , in candelas;
$I_n(C, \gamma)$	is the normalize luminous intensity of the luminaire at direction specified by angular coordinates (C, γ) , in candelas per lumen;
$r(\tan \epsilon, \beta)$	is the reduced luminance coefficient for the incident light path with angular coordinates (ϵ, β) , in reciprocal steradians;
f_M	is the luminaire overall maintenance factor, unit 1;
Φ	is the luminous flux of the luminaire, in lumen;
H	is the mounting height of the luminaire above the surface of the road, in metres.

Considering the luminous intensity distribution:

- the manufacture tolerances of a luminaire is generally given considering its rated luminous flux and a nominal luminous intensity distribution;
- luminaires with flux control can work at the rated luminous flux while their luminous intensity distribution can change with aging;
- it helps to identify a photometric contribution (luminous flux) and a geometric contribution (direction of lighting) that depends on mounting tolerances (mounting height of the luminaire, inter-distance between columns, rotation, orientation and tilt of the luminaire)
- tolerances on the luminaire luminous flux and on the luminous intensity distribution can rise from different physical causes: for example, in traditional luminaires, respectively the luminous flux of the source and the source position respect to the reflect focus, in LED luminaire respectively the total luminous flux and the ratio between the luminous flux of the single chips or the mechanical position of the LED module.
- the luminaire aging can modify quite independently the luminous flux value and the normalized luminous intensity distribution.

For our aims the luminaire overall maintenance factor is not important. It can be disregarded or considered equal to 1.

With these considerations the above formula becomes:

$$L = \frac{I(C, \gamma) q(\epsilon, \beta) (\cos \epsilon)^3}{H^2} = \frac{I_n(C, \gamma) \Phi q(\epsilon, \beta) (\cos \epsilon)^3}{H^2}$$

To evaluate analytically the influence of the tolerances or measurement uncertainties of the quantities in the above equation to the road surface luminance L , we follow the approach described in annex A of the European standard.

In order to simplify the problem, we consider the position of point p and the luminaire mounting height H as given without uncertainty or tolerance. In this way both the directions (C, γ) and (ϵ, β) are exactly known. This is equivalent to the hypothesis adopted when calculations are carried out during the design phase following the algorithm described in ⁵⁷

Following the algorithm and nomenclature given in annex A⁵⁷, the combined relative tolerance of road surface luminance L is:

$$\frac{u_c(L)}{L} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u(I_n)}{I_n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(\Phi)}{\Phi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(q)}{q}\right)^2}$$

where:

- $\frac{u(I_n)}{I_n}$ is the relative uncertainty of the normalised luminous intensity of the luminaire at the given direction, unit 1;
- $\frac{u(\Phi)}{\Phi}$ is the relative uncertainty of the luminous flux of the luminaire, unit 1;
- $\frac{u(q)}{q}$ is the relative uncertainty of the luminance coefficient at the given lighting and view conditions, unit 1.

The above equation is correct for the given lighting and view conditions where all the formula parameters are known. In this situation, where only one direction of emission of the luminaire is considered, the uncertainty of the normalised luminous intensity can be discarded and thought as included in the luminous flux uncertainty. This permits to compare the influence of these two uncertainties in the combined tolerance, as show in. In the left diagram the lower limit of the relative uncertainty of the luminous flux can be considered as the best luminaire characterization a laboratory can declare, while the upper limit is comparable to values required in many standards. The diagram on the right can be used to select, for a given maximum level of acceptable tolerance of the road surface luminance, the limiting tolerances or uncertainties of the other two quantities. These two diagrams clearly justify the necessity to measure the road luminance coefficient when the installation over-dimensioning shall be reduced and give an evaluation of the level of *accuracy* can be expected in the results of a design calculation.

Figure 24 The relative tolerance in the luminance value versus the uncertainty in the knowledge of the road luminance coefficient and luminaire luminous flux

For comparison with measurement surveys of the road lighting installation performance this model is too simple: for example in the real world also the luminaire mounting have a tolerance. For a complete evaluation, the algorithm as described in EN standard⁵⁷ shall be follow. The obtained tolerance of L can be explained as

a “manufacturing” tolerance of the installation (the road lighting installation performances are within this tolerance range) or as a calculation uncertainty (the road lighting characteristics permits to evaluate its performances with this uncertainty range).

6.3 Spectral properties of the pavement

The knowledge of road surface spectral reflectance is useful for different applications, not limited to road lighting and mesopic implementation. Road surfaces are also suitable as non-variant targets or pseudo-invariant targets during the calibration/validation of remotely-sensed images⁵⁸. For this reason, remote sensing (imaging and hyperspectral) is widely used in addition to the on-site and laboratory spectral reflectometry.

Remote imaging spectrometry has been utilized for transportation studies, because of its ability to provide means to derive physical and chemical properties of materials, assess different pavement characteristics including age and conditions. It also acts as reference for image calibration and validation of satellite surveys⁵⁹.

A large spectral library of road surface spectral reflectance is available online⁶⁰, typical reflection spectra show that concrete surface material exhibits the highest reflection in the visible wavelength range. Road materials like gravel and asphalt have lower reflectance, approximately 20 % and 10 %, respectively, which makes it possible to identify the pavement material used for roads. However, in the infrared wavelength range the reflectance of concrete and gravel pavements become equal at around 1 400 nm, and it is decreasing towards longer wavelengths. This behaviour has obvious relevance in the environmental monitoring and urban heat island mitigation strategies⁶¹.

In the blue part of the spectrum (wavelengths <500 nm), the reflectance decreases: with rapid decrease by about a factor of two for concrete and gravel. Some measurements have shown that around a wavelength of 450 nm, the reflectance of concrete and gravel are even equal. The reflectance of asphalt decreases at blue wavelengths and its impact on the mesopic concept application, is analysed in Surface deliverable D6.

The large variation of spectral behaviour shown in the data of the spectral library, is mainly due to the variability of substrates^{62,63}: asphalt pavements consist of rocky components and asphalt mix (or hot mix or bitumen). The mineral constituents of the rocky components can vary depending on the geological region, usual major components in the aggregate are SiO₂, CaO, and MgO. The asphalt mix is a complex substance that can vary in composition depending on the source of the crude oil and on the refining process.

In brand new asphalt, the surface is completely sealed with asphalt mix and the spectral reflectance is generally low with a minimum near 350 nm, with a linear rise towards longer wavelengths. With aging, the reflectance increases: 10-year old asphalt reflects about twice of that of 1-year old asphalt pavement. However, cracks, raveling, and erosion may also affect the reflectance⁶³.

Figure 25. Spectral effects of the asphalt surface characteristics of aging from the ASD ground spectral measurements (the major water-vapor absorption bands are interpolated). A, asphalt aging and erosion; B, structural road damages (cracks); C, structural road damages (raveling); D, pavement maintenance. From Ref. ⁶³.

In diagram B, the three curves C, D and E illustrate the effect of cracks on the reflectance of pavement. It can be seen that presence of cracks in the road pavement has an effect on spectral reflectance: high severity cracking of pavement causes reflectance decrease by about 1.5 times.

In diagram C, the three curves F, G and H depict the effect of road damages on the reflectance of pavement. It can be seen that presence of damages on the road pavement has an effect on spectral reflectance: gravel and raveling of pavement causes an increase of reflectance. The increase is more pronounced in the visible part of the spectrum.

In diagram D, the four curves C, I, J, and K illustrate the effect of road maintenance on the reflectance of pavement. It can be seen that the spectral reflectance depends on the material, as well as the method of road maintenance: fresh asphalt and crack seal (curves I and J) exhibit lower reflectance, compared to that of 10-year old pavement (curve C). Chip seal of 3-years age (curve K) causes pavement reflectance to increase about 1.5 times, compared to that of 10-year old pavement (curve C).

6.4 Impact of the lamp spectral power distribution

Every light source would produce, with regards to its Spectral Power Distribution (SPD), different measured values of the luminance coefficient of pavements of not spectrally neutral reflectance. Unfortunately, there is not a defined reference source.

Different sources are involved in the metrology of road surfaces: the lamp used for measuring the reflectance properties (on site or in laboratory) and the lamp used for the calibration of the measuring device.

From the review of currently available instruments for road surface measurements, it was established that no common light source is generally used. Available instruments use LED sources, discharge lamps and also incandescent lamps (CIE standard illuminant A).

The SURFACE consortium investigated the impact of the instrument light source SPD on the luminance coefficient measured values and on the evaluated uncertainty.

6.4.1 Methodology

To evaluate the impact of the SPD of the lamp used to measure the Luminance Coefficient, the relative luminance coefficient of a set of road surfaces of known spectral reflectance was calculated for different lighting sources.

The Relative Luminance Coefficient C_r is defined as:

$$C_r = \frac{\int_{380}^{780} R(\lambda) \times SPD(\lambda) \times V(\lambda) \times d\lambda}{\int_{380}^{780} SPD(\lambda) \times V(\lambda) \times d\lambda} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- $V(\lambda)$: CIE spectral luminous efficiency for photopic vision (i.e. the CIE 1931 2° Standard Observer).
- $SPD(\lambda)$: Relative spectral power density of the light source normalised to its peak value.
- $R(\lambda)$: Spectral bidirectional reflectance function (BRDF) of road surface, namely the spectral luminance coefficient of the pavement for a given direction of illumination and for the geometry of observation $\alpha = 1^\circ$.

The change in the Relative Luminance Coefficient C_r reflects the impact of the lighting source on the luminance coefficient $Q = L/E$, where L is the luminance reflected from the lighting producing the illuminance E .

In order to extend the analysis of the impact of the lighting source spectrum, a large database of 184 different lighting source spectra, representing most of the available lighting technologies (LED, Metal Halide, High-pressure Sodium, Low-pressure Sodium, Fluorescent, Xenon pulsed, mercury vapour, halogen), was tested on a test set of nine road pavements with known spectral reflectance, see Figure 26.

Figure 26. Spectral reflectance of the test set of nine road pavements used in the calculations.

To improve the knowledge on the impact of LED spectrum, an additional sub-set of spectra of several LED technologies have also been tested.

6.4.2 Impact of source SPD on the measured values

For each light source, the mean C_r value of the test set road surfaces was calculated, and the relative deviation of each road, computed. The results are shown in Figure 27 for general light sources, and in Figure 28 for a specific sub-set of LED sources.

a)

b)

Figure 27. a) Deviations of the Relative Luminance Coefficient and b) standard deviations, of test set road surfaces for the different light sources.

a)

b)

Figure 28. a) Deviations of the Relative Luminance Coefficient of each road surface and b) standard deviations, of test set road surfaces for different LED sources.

From the above figures, the conclusions are:

- *RGB LED, Low-pressure Sodium, High-pressure Sodium, and Xenon Pulsed light sources present the largest deviations from the mean, from -3 % up to +4 %, and dispersions with respect to pavements*
- *Metal Halide (CCT = 3610 K) and Halogen (CCT = 3000 K) light sources present the lowest deviations from the mean and dispersions with respect to pavements. Absolute deviation is < 0.15 % for halogen and ≤ 0.1 % for Metal Halide.*
- *Neutral LEDs present the lowest deviations from the mean (± 0.3 %) and dispersions with respect to pavements and that for all light sources, deviation are comprised in the interval [-1 %, +2 %].*

To highlight the impact of the sources on the test set, the cumulated values are shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Cumulated values of the different light sources on the test set road surfaces.

It is to note that these values are useful, since the same considerations may be applied to the inverse case; the computation of luminance values of a road of given spectral properties at the lighting design stage.

To conclude:

- *The design of a lighting system with RGB LED, Low-pressure Sodium, High-pressure Sodium, and Xenon Pulsed is statistically more affected by the spectral behaviour of road surfaces*
- *The design of a lighting system equipped with LED sources, especially neutral LED (i.e. Blue LED and phosphor) leads to low discrepancies (in the range -1 % to +2 %, which is half compared to the above sources)*

6.4.3 Impact of source SPD on the calculated uncertainty values

As said above, every light source would produce, with regards to its SPD, different measured values of the luminance coefficient of pavements of not spectrally neutral reflectance. Currently there is no defined reference light source for measurement and every instrument has its own, relying on the calibration to compensate for all spectral discrepancies. Unfortunately, detector deviations from $V(\lambda)$ and impact of SPD are not usually considered: the SURFACE consortium therefore investigated the impact on the measurement uncertainty of SPD on non-neutral road surface reflectance.

Assuming that a reference light source, of given SPD, ensures the minimum deviation on all road surfaces of the test set (Figure 26). The luminance coefficient of a pavement measured with another type of light source, other than the reference light source, will present a departure from the luminance computed with the reference coefficient, this deviation can be within the boundaries expressed by the calculations performed with a large set of lighting sources.

To establish these boundaries and observe the statistical effect of lighting SPD on the determination of the luminance coefficient, the distribution of the luminance coefficients for the test set road surface is calculated (A) for the large set of 184 light sources SPD and (B) for the reduced set where the SPD are varied by a random quantity through a basic Monte-Carlo Method (MCM), see Table 7.

Table 7. Test road surface luminance coefficient boundaries for large set of 184 SPD, case A calculations.

Pavement ID	Mean Value	Standard deviation (%)	Coeff. interval max - min (%)	Min (%)	Max (%)
SMA_16_W2	0.4212	0.29	2.04	-0.83	+1.22
SMA_18_L2	0.2706	0.80	5.59	-1.72	+3.87
SMA_18_L1	0.2247	0.86	5.88	-1.83	+4.05
SMA_16	0.1824	0.96	6.82	-2.10	+4.72
SMA_16_W1	0.3258	0.47	3.38	-1.31	+2.06
SMA_16_W3	0.4069	0.50	3.50	-1.47	+2.03
Ech_486	0.2538	0.28	1.96	-0.85	+1.11
Ech_822	0.1177	0.39	2.34	-0.95	+1.40
Ech_924	0.2045	0.51	3.15	-1.24	+1.91

To test the influence on the uncertainty, the SPD of a reduced set of sources was modified by a normal distribution with a standard deviation of 10 % of the peak value by MCM. The mean value, standard deviation and interval of the luminance coefficient was calculated, see Table 8.

Table 8. Luminance coefficient mean value, standard deviation and interval calculated with MCM of the variation of three given light sources SPD.

Lighting	_2900K_Mitsubishi		_2_1_N		Xenon_pulsed	
Pavement	SMA_16	Ech_486	SMA_16	Ech_486	SMA_16	Ech_486
Mean Value Luminance coefficient	0.182	0.254	0.182	0.254	0.178	0.252
Standard deviation (%)	0.198	0.054	0.116	0.030	0.191	0.059
Coeff. interval (%)	0.861	0.299	0.512	0.156	0.895	0.265

The conclusion from simulation is:

- *The SPD variations considered in the MCM simulation do not reach the large variations of luminance coefficients obtained with a large set of real lighting SPD, unless applying very strong deviations with no physical meaning*
- *Global shape changes of SPD have more impact than local variations*
- *Deviations and discrepancies depend more on the pavement characteristics, (i.e. the SMA_16 being spectrally less flat than the Ech_486 pavement) than on actual SPD variations*

7 CONCLUSIONS

Table 9 collects all SURFACE suggestions presented in this guideline:

Table 9. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Geometries of measurement – angle of observation	<p>Extra-urban road: 1°, viewing distance of 85.9 m</p> <p>Urban road: 2.29°, viewing distance of 37.5 m</p> <p>Urban driving at low speed: 5°, viewing distance of 17 m, suitable for cycling and scooters</p> <p>Boundary between diffuse and specular behaviour: 10° and 20° are under consideration</p>
Metrological requirement for instruments for <i>r</i> -tables	<p>A measurement geometry that corresponds to the norm (observation angle) [1°, 2.29°]</p> <p>A measure that is representative of the surface (i.e. an average over enough points) [100 cm²]</p> <p>Good collimation, i.e. small angular subtense of the light source [$<0.2^\circ$]</p> <p>Small detector angular subtense, i.e. good telecentricity of the detector [$<0.08^\circ$ cf CIE 66-1984]</p>
Uncertainty evaluation	<p>Good calibration of the different elements</p> <p>Determination of the values of the relevant parameters contributing to the uncertainty</p> <p>LUMCORUN software</p>
Laboratory measurement procedure	
Sample identification and extraction	<p>Reference the position of the extraction</p> <p>Avoid evident heterogenous area</p> <p>Clean the sample on-site with water after extraction (if dirt or mud introduced by the extraction process)</p> <p>Identify the circulation direction with a mark</p>
Transport and storage	<p>Place samples in conditions to maintain state</p> <p>Cover with protective material during transport</p> <p>Store samples indoors, preferably in a controlled temperature room, upside down and covered</p> <p>Do not expose samples to direct sunlight</p>
Alignment	<p>Ensure that the positioning of the source, sample and detector are correct with regards to each other</p> <p>The centre of the sample (P) is the centre of the measurement</p> <p>Place the surface of the sample in the reference plane, corresponding to the measured plane</p>

Table 9. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Recording	<p>Sample: identification code and date of extraction, condition of storage, washing actions</p> <p>Laboratory: environmental conditions including temperature and humidity, any other relevant conditions including lamp control. Depending on the type of light source used, it should be warmed-up to ensure a better stability.</p> <p>Measuring device: time of switch-on of the device (including lamp) and time of start and end of measurement, and if used, reference material used for initial setup</p>
On site measurement procedure	
Road	<p>Figure 14 shows all necessary information to be recorded about the measurement site and the road</p> <p>Road must be not used by vehicles at the time of measurement</p> <p>Environmental conditions: outside temperature above +5 °C, avoid fog</p>
Selection of the measurement area	<p>Chose a planar area without defects, use the suggested contour gauge to identify convexities</p> <p>Pavement must be dry, unsalted</p> <p>Measurement shall be done in the direction of circulation</p>
Sampling	<p>Sampling: on each lane of circulation, in the centre and in the tyre tracks.</p> <p>Choose several sampling areas and perform at least 6 measurements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 in the tyre track and 3 on the centre track. - If it is possible to make more measurements, it is better. - The advice is to make the same number of measurements in the tyre track and in the centre track.
Recording	<p>Place and conditions of measurement: type of road and its use, traffic, date, meteorological conditions (e.g. cloudy, sunny, windy, etc.), environmental conditions, including temperature, humidity and dew point if available</p> <p>Type of pavement describing its general aspects (Is it dirty? Are the tyre tracks visible?) and all available information as its age, size and colour of the granulate, type of binder, special surface treatment, etc.</p> <p>Pictures with a general view and more close-up view with a pencil or a grid to provide a size and a colour scale, including a picture with the contour gauge</p>
Data analysis	

Table 9. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Measured data and statistics	<p>Measured values depend on: heterogeneity of the surface along the road length because of the construction process and the weather exposure, type of asphalt and binder, traffic, usage, ageing, and on the measured place (centre track or tyre track).</p> <p>Avoid a mean value of the <i>r</i>-table, because it may not be representative of a physical surface</p> <p>Provide the most representative <i>r</i>-tables (considering the shape of the solid) and the extremes, i.e. three values</p> <p>Devices measuring only Q_0 and S_1, provide the mean value and standard deviation</p> <p>Possible statistical approaches:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Calculate the mean of all measurements and the standard deviation to quantify the road heterogeneity B. Differentiate the statistics for the centre track and tyre track: calculate the average and standard deviation for each C. Calculate a weighted average: Make a ponderation between measurement on the centre track and tyre track with a weight of 2/3 on the centre track and 1/3 on the tyre track to represent the percentage of each case on the road D. Choose an <i>r</i>-table which is representative of all the measurements. This last approach has the advantage of the choice of a real physical table instead of an artificial table done with the mean of all the <i>r</i> factors (mathematically incorrect because a weighted average is done to calculate Q_0) <p>If the classical lighting design approach is used (one typical CIE <i>r</i>-table with a scaling of Q_0), the measured <i>r</i>-table is not used but only Q_0 and S_1 factors. Thus, the average of the measured Q_0, S_1 factors could be used, using one of the preceding approaches (A, B or C). As in CIE144, the average of S_1 is used to choose the typical table and the average of Q_0 will add the scaling factor. To characterise the heterogeneity of the road, provide the mean value and also the standard deviation.</p> <p>If the actual <i>r</i>-table of the pavement could be used in the lighting design, it is recommended to choose a representative measured <i>r</i>-table instead of an average (approach D). It will provide a more physically realistic BRDF. This table is the closest from the average of the S_1 factor, makes physical sense and could be scaled according to the average of the Q_0 factor. To characterise the heterogeneity of the road, provide the mean value, and also the extremes.</p>

Table 9. SURFACE project suggestions and recommendations.

TOPIC	SURFACE Suggestions
Impact of additional pavement conditions	<p>Additional influences:</p> <p>Time, traffic: the centre track is slightly darker and less specular than the tyre track</p> <p>Difficult to isolate the effect of traffic from the time and ambient conditions</p> <p>Studies show that Q_0 and S_1 are bigger in the circulated part of the road</p> <p>With salt or dust, the specularity is generally lower</p>
Spectral properties	
Influence of the sources vs spectral reflectance of pavements	<p>The design of a lighting system with RGB LED, low-pressure Sodium, high-pressure Sodium, and Xenon Pulsed is statistically more affected by the spectral behaviour of road surfaces</p> <p>The design of a lighting system equipped with LED sources, especially neutral LED (i.e. blue LED and phosphor) leads to low discrepancies (in the range -1 % to +2 %, which is half compared to the aforementioned sources)</p>

8 REFERENCES

1. Road Statistics. Yearbook 2017 Road Statistics; European Union Road Federation: Brussels, Belgium, 2017., http://www.erf.be/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Road_statistics_2017.pdf (accessed 28 March 2019).
2. CIE 066:1984 *Road surfaces and lighting (joint technical report CIE/PIARC)*. CIE, <http://cie.co.at/publications/road-surfaces-and-lighting-joint-technical-report-ciepiarc> (1984, accessed 12 March 2020).
3. EN 13201-2:2015. Road lighting - Part 2: Performance requirements.
4. EN 13201-3:2015. Road lighting - Part 3: Calculation of performance.
5. CIE 144-2001 *Road surface and road marking reflection characteristics*. Technical Report, CIE, 2001.
6. Muzet V, Colomb M, Toinette M, et al. Towards an optimization of urban lighting through a combined approach of lighting and road building activities. In: *PROCEEDINGS OF the 29th Quadrennial Session of the CIE*. Washington DC, USA: International Commission on Illumination, CIE, pp. 789–800.
7. Fotios S, Boyce P, Ellis C. The Effect of Pavement Material on Road Lighting Performance. *Light. J. Rugby*, 2006, p. 35.
8. GREEN PAPER Lighting the Future Accelerating the deployment of innovative lighting technologies, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/GA/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0889> (2011, accessed 12 March 2020).
9. EN 13201-5:2015. Road lighting - Part 5: Energy performance indicators.
10. Chain C, Lopez F, Verny P. Impact of real road photometry on public lighting design. Beijing, China: CIE, 2007.
11. Dumont E, Paumier J-L. Are standard tables r still representative of the properties of road surfaces in France? Beijing, China: CIE, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/278805068_Are_standard_r-tables_still_representative_of_road_surface_photometric_characteristics_in_France (2007).
12. Muzet V, Greffier F, Nicolăi A, et al. Evaluation of the performance of an optimized road surface/lighting combination: *Lighting Research & Technology* 2018; 51: 576–591.
13. Muzet V, Abdo J. On Site Photometric Characterisation of Cement Concrete Pavements with COLUROUTE Device. *Light and Engineering* 2018; 26: 88–94.
14. NRM02 SURFACE. SURFACE, <https://surface-nrm02.eu/> (2020, accessed 19 March 2020).
15. Iacomussi P, Rossi G, Blattner P, et al. Metrology of Road Surface for Smart Lighting. pp. 103–107.
16. CIE 030:1976 Calculation and Measurement of Luminance and Illuminance in Road Lighting, <http://cie.co.at/publications/calculation-and-measurement-luminance-and-illuminance-road-lighting> (1976, accessed 16 March 2020).
17. CIE 030.2:1982 Calculation and Measurement of Luminance and Illuminance in Road Lighting, <http://cie.co.at/publications/calculation-and-measurement-luminance-and-illuminance-road-lighting> (1982, accessed 16 March 2020).

18. CIE 140:2000 Road Lighting Calculations, https://www.techstreet.com/cie/standards/cie-140-2000?product_id=1210058 (2000, accessed 18 March 2020).
19. Gašparovský D, Janiga P, Korobko A, et al. *CIE 140:2019 Road Lighting Calculations, 2nd Edition*. CIE 140:2019, International Commission on Illumination (CIE). Epub ahead of print 5 February 2019. DOI: 10.25039/TR.140.2019.
20. de Boer JB, Schreuder DA. Glare as a Criterion for Quality in Street Lighting. *Transactions of the Illuminating Engineering Society* 1967; 32: 117–135.
21. EN 1436:2018 Road marking materials - Road marking performance for road users and test methods, https://standards.cen.eu/dyn/www/f?p=204:110:0:::FSP_PROJECT,FSP_ORG_ID:38680,6207&cs=16797DA848BEEA8069D9DCB4A14215C2D (2018, accessed 12 March 2020).
22. Sørensen K, Obro P, Rasmussen B. A review of the suitability of the average luminance coefficient Q_0 for road surfaces and road markings – and proposal for a different parameter.
23. Sørensen K. Q_0 and Q_d – “lightness” of road surfaces in road lighting.
24. Brusque C, Carta C. Etude comparative des paramètres Q_0 et Q_d décrivant la clarté des revêtements routiers: typologie et modélisation des caractéristiques photométriques des matériaux.
25. Gibbons RB. *Influence of Pavement Reflection on Target Visibility*. Ph. D., University of Waterloo, <https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/bitstream/handle/10012/244/NQ30612.pdf;jsessionid=5F6A72A0A5E637C486605A714AC78931?sequence=1> (1997).
26. Chain C, Marchaut V. R-tables for other observation angles: specific needs for two applications in the field of public lighting. CIE, 2008.
27. NF P98-351 August 2010 Footways - Integration of disabled people - caution warning - Characteristics, testing and rules for ground installation of pedotactile caution warning devices for blind or partially sighted persons, <https://www.boutique.afnor.org/standard/nf-p98-351/footways-integration-of-disabled-people-caution-warning-characteristics-testing-and-rules-for-ground-installation-of-pedotactile/article/775517/fa140125> (2010, accessed 12 March 2020).
28. Fotios S, Uttley J, Cheal C, et al. Using eye-tracking to identify pedestrians’ critical visual tasks, Part 1. Dual task approach. *Lighting Research & Technology* 2014; 47: 133–148.
29. Fotios S, Castleton HF. Lighting for cycling in the UK—A review. *Lighting Research & Technology* 2015; 49: 381–395.
30. Patla AE, Vickers JN. How far ahead do we look when required to step on specific locations in the travel path during locomotion? *Exp Brain Res* 2003; 148: 133–138.
31. Fotios S, Uttley J. Illuminance required to detect a pavement obstacle of critical size: *Lighting Research & Technology*. Epub ahead of print 20 July 2016. DOI: 10.1177/1477153516659783.
32. Stockmar A. Extension of the luminance concept in road and tunnel lighting. Manchester, United Kingdom: CIE, 2015, pp. 751–753.
33. Sørensen K, Ekrias A, Hafdell P, et al. Reflection properties of road surfaces in Denmark, <https://nmfv.dk/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/Reflection-properties-of-road-surfaces-in-Denmark-version-17-May-2017-1.pdf> (2017).

34. Greffier F, Muzet V, Boucher V, et al. Use of an imaging luminance measuring device to evaluate road lighting performance at different angles of observation. In: *PROCEEDINGS OF the 29th Quadrennial Session of the CIE*. Washington DC, USA: International Commission on Illumination, CIE, pp. 553–562.
35. Waldram JM. The calculation of sky haze luminance from street lighting: *Lighting Research & Technology* 2016; 4: 21–26.
36. Crawford DL (ed). Light Pollution, Radio Interference, and Space Debris, http://www.aspbbooks.org/a/volumes/table_of_contents/?book_id=129 (1991, accessed 12 March 2020).
37. Garstang RH. Dust and light pollution. *PASP* 1991; 103: 1109.
38. Soardo P, Iacomussi P, Rossi G, et al. Compatibility of road lighting with star visibility: *Lighting Research & Technology* 2008; 40: 307–322.
39. Gidlund H, Lindgren M, Muzet V, et al. Road Surface Photometric Characterisation and Its Impact on Energy Savings. *Coatings* 2019; 9: 286.
40. Soardo P, Iacomussi P, Rossi G. The luminance coefficient in road lighting. A parameter to save energy and reducing atmospheric pollution. Istanbul, 2009.
41. *CIE 150:2017 Guide on the limitation of the effects of obtrusive light from outdoor lighting installations, Second Edition*. CIE, https://www.techstreet.com/cie/standards/cie-150-2017?product_id=1997388 (2017, accessed 12 March 2020).
42. XP X90 013: 2011 XP external light pollution - control and calculation methods, https://infostore.saiglobal.com/en-gb/Standards/XP-X90-013-2011-XP-73182_SAIG_AFNOR_AFNOR_155044/ (2011, accessed 12 March 2020).
43. Accueil | Sécurité Routière, <https://www.securite-routiere.gouv.fr/> (accessed 23 June 2020).
44. Decreto_Ministeriale_numero_6792_05-11-2001_all_1.pdf, http://www.mit.gov.it/sites/default/files/media/normativa/2016-02/Decreto_Ministeriale_numero_6792_05-11-2001_all_1.pdf (accessed 23 June 2020).
45. 2020_030_vgu_begrepp_och_grundvarden.pdf, https://trafikverket.ineko.se/Files/sv-SE/71831/Ineko.Product.RelatedFiles/2020_030_vgu_begrepp_och_grundvarden.pdf (accessed 23 June 2020).
46. VSS-40551-1 / 2019 - VSS, <http://shop.mobilityplatform.ch/de/shop/show-item/product/27295/> (accessed 23 June 2020).
47. International vocabulary of metrology – Basic and general concepts and associated terms. (VIM). 3rd edition, VIM JCGM200.
48. Muzet V, Bernasconi J, Iacomussi P, et al. Review of road surface photometry methods and devices – Proposal for new measurement geometries. *Lighting Research & Technology* 2020; 1477153520958454.
49. Jackett M, Frith W. Reflection properties of new zealand road surfaces for road lighting design. 2010, p. 15.
50. Li W, Zheng S, Demirdes H. New achievements in practical determination of road surface reflection table from in situ measurements. In: *Proceeding of 28th CIE Session 2015*. Manchester, UK, 2015, pp. 1676–1681.

51. Muzet V, Greffier F, Nicolai A, et al. Evaluation of the performance of an optimized road surface/lighting combination: *Lighting Research & Technology* 2018; 51: 576–591.
52. Ekrias A. *Road Surface Reflection Properties*. Helsinki: Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency, May 2019.
53. Schreuder D. A portable reflectometer for on the road measurements. Experiences from the Netherlands. TURIN, ITALY: CIE, 2008.
54. Strbac-Hadzibegovic N, Strbac-Savic S, Kostic M. A new procedure for determining the road surface reduced luminance coefficient table by on-site measurements. *Lighting Research & Technology* 2018; 51: 65–81.
55. Muzet V, Abdo J. On Site Photometric Characterisation of Cement Concrete Pavements with COLUROUTE Device. *Light and Engineering* 2018; 26: 88–94.
56. Jackett M, Frith W. Measurement of the reflection properties of road surfaces to improve the safety and sustainability of road lighting. *NZ Transport Agency research report 383*.
57. EN 13201-4:2015. Road lighting - Part 4: Methods of measuring lighting performance.
58. Mei A, Salvatori R, Fiore N, et al. Integration of Field and Laboratory Spectral Data with Multi-Resolution Remote Sensed Imagery for Asphalt Surface Differentiation. *Remote Sensing* 2014; 6: 2765–2781.
59. Novack T, Esch T, Kux H, et al. Machine Learning Comparison between WorldView-2 and QuickBird-2-Simulated Imagery Regarding Object-Based Urban Land Cover Classification. *Remote Sensing* 2011; 3: 2263–2282.
60. Santa Barbara Asphalt Road Spectral Library, http://www.geo-informatie.nl/Projects/Santa_Barbara_Urban_Spectral_Library/urbanspec/road_spec.htm (accessed 24 September 2020).
61. Rossi G, Iacomussi P, Zinzi M. Lighting Implications of Urban Mitigation Strategies through Cool Pavements: Energy Savings and Visual Comfort. *Climate* 2018; 6: 26.
62. Herold M, Roberts DA, Gardner ME, et al. Spectrometry for urban area remote sensing—Development and analysis of a spectral library from 350 to 2400 nm. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 2004; 91: 304–319.
63. Herold M, Roberts D. Spectral characteristics of asphalt road aging and deterioration: implications for remote-sensing applications. *Appl Opt* 2005; 44: 4327.